

ECONOMIC VALUATION OF HARPAN KHOLA SUB-WATERSHED AT PANCHASE MOUNTAIN ECOSYSTEM, NEPAL – A WILLINGNESS TO PAY MODE OF PAYMENT

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Abstract

An ecosystem is a dynamic system that is made up of living things and their surroundings, and ecosystem services are the benefits that people get from it. Nepal's Panchase Forest Region was given an economic value, and the Logit Regression model was used to look at the data. The study showed that even though protecting forests has been the government's top goal, what was really needed was better forest management. For the study, the "Willingness to Pay" (WTP) mode of payment was taken into account. WTP was related to the age of the people, the number of visits by household members, the cost of loss caused by uncontrolled forest growth, and the distance from the closest market. WTP was lower when there were more family members who needed help, when homes spent money, and when NGOs and INGOs helped. With a demand graph that slope downward, the forest was in good shape.

Keywords: ES (Ecosystem Services), WTP (Willingness to Pay), CB (Cost-Benefit), CVM (Contingent Valuation Method)

I. INTRODUCTION

An ecosystem is a dynamic complex formed by the interaction of living components, such as plant, animal, and microorganism communities, and their nonliving environment (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003). The benefits people obtain from the ecosystem are defined as ecosystem services (ES) (Millennium Ecosystem Assessment, 2003). The idea of ecosystem services has been refined in the past to include not only those services that humans get opportunistically from nature but also services from ecological systems that humans manage directly (Antle et. al, 2001).

Human beings are supposed to be the most intelligent beings on earth and unfortunately, they have been the most destructive agents living on the earth too. The examples can be from the development of atom bombs, which were supposed to be created for human security and used in the World Wars, to the exploitation of nature and the ecosystem for personal use. Human beings are an important dimension for the overall ecosystem balance and though the negative impacts of human interventions might be seen in nature only by now, it is the human beings only who will be affected in the long run. Human beings have been dependent on the natural ecosystem for several reasons- ranging from

the agricultural lands for food production to the recreational services for livelihood. Once an ecosystem is affected, the above-mentioned attributes are also to be affected which is after all connected to the individual economy and ultimately to the national economy.

Forests produce benefits to society such as timber, recreational opportunities, open space, wildlife habitat, and air and water purification. Non-use and non-market services provided by forests including the cycling of clean air and water supplies and provisions of habitat for flora, fish, and fauna do not come with a price, are essentially free, and are seldom accounted. The fundamental environmental-economic problem with forestland conversion is that the loss in ecosystem services is not paid for by those who benefit from the conversion because those benefits are external to the market factors of supply and demand.

Consider forestland growing near a rural residential area that can be used for sustainable forest management or converted into roads and new housing development. Forestland is bought and sold in markets; however, the market demand for forestland is based on the private benefits that flow to the sellers, such as revenues from timber harvest or from selling land to a developer. The market ignores the benefits received by others who do not pay for them. Further, it ignores the costs to society of benefits lost as a result of such transactions. Since the demand for forestland does not reflect the benefits of intact forests that flow to society, the market will allocate less forest than the socially optimal amount.

The value of ecosystem services depends on the role of ecological properties in attaining human goals in a given certain socio-economic context (Barbier, et al., 2009). Human incentives for utilizing and manipulating ecosystem services are driven by ES values in the form of market price, private nonmarket benefits, and social institutions (Robertson & Swinton, 2005). For the ecosystem services that are derived in the form of agricultural services, the valuation can be easy as different level of incentives can be identified and total value can be calculated but in the case of non-real-market based ecosystem services, the non-market valuation of ecosystem services benefits is needed to calculate the total value. The explanation of nonmarket valuation methods for ecosystem services and preferred methods for different ES can be found in Barbier et al. (2009).

The complexities related to communities with low-incomes, higher rates of unemployment, the existence of informal markets, and limited access to formal financial institutions are yet to be tackled. Yet, to ensure the successful implementation of CEs in rural areas these issues need to be addressed. To date, this has not been achieved as existing CE studies have focused on urban areas in developing countries, and a willingness-to-accept format in rural areas (Adhikari et al., 2005; Casey et al., 2008; Brouwer et al., 2010). In the rural context of developing countries, the criticisms and limitations of implementing stated preference surveys to estimate the value of non-market services seem particularly valid.

A positive relationship between WTP for non-market forest benefits and income of respondents (Lehtonen et al., 2003; Wang et al., 2007), indicates income-poor households have a relatively lower WTP or prefer to free ride in their use of forest services. However, the success stories of community-based natural resource

management programs signify their contribution to and benefits received from forest management (Ostrom, 1990). Also, it is widely observed that respondents, particularly forest users and rural inhabitants, have higher WTP for forest ecosystem services compared to non-users and urban residents (Hanley et al., 1998; Brey et al., 2007; Christie et al., 2007). The challenge is determining how to incorporate the potential contribution and concerns of members of subsistence communities into a non-market valuation framework.

Valuation studies using the contingent valuation method have occasionally used non-monetary numéraires including time and in-kind goods such as rice and beehives to estimate the value of non-market benefits to address the cash constraint problem in developing countries (Shyamsundar and Kramer, 1996; Mekonnen, 2000; Alam, 2006; Asquith et al., 2008; Saxena et al., 2008; Shiappacasse et al., 2010; Tilahun et al., 2011). This study uses labor contribution as an alternate cost attribute as it is more appropriate for the forest-dependent communities which are the focus of the study. Usually, in an agrarian community, labor contributions have a social acceptance and farm-households allocate labor for different purposes such as forestry, farming, work for wages, and self-employment to optimize their benefits (Jacoby, 1993; Abdulai and Delgado, 1999; Alam, 2006). The elicited willingness-to-contribute (WTC) in labor terms can be monetized to estimate the dollar value of non-market services (Hung et al., 2007; O'Garra, 2009).

Using time as a cost attribute in a CE survey faces a theoretical challenge as an aggregation of the monetary value on the number of labor-days declared by the respondents is sensitive to the value of labor contribution which is situation-dependent (Ahlheim et al., 2010). There are several strategies in practice to estimate the money value of time. For instance, O'Garra (2009) proposed the rate of conversion by assessing the nature of the trade-off —whether the individual makes a trade-off time spent contributing towards the environmental program with work time or leisure time —while eliciting WTP. Eom and Larson (2006) estimated the shadow value of time using the contingent valuation method, and Rai and Scarborough (2012) used a choice experiment.

Theoretically, when choices are constrained by both time and money, WTP can be elicited using either numéraire (Eom and Larson, 2006). The main aim of stated preference surveys is to carry-out social cost-benefit analysis of environmental projects; therefore, the challenge of putting a dollar value on the labor contribution associated with different shadow values across individuals should not hinder the efforts for extending CE. Instead, using time as a numéraire contributes to making CE accessible to income-poor populations and allows them to participate in environmental decision-making (Farley and Brown, 2007).

There are several analyses done for the ecosystem services but the valuation of the ecosystem services has not been an entertained issue in the research paradigm of Nepal. Previous studies on ecosystem services have been focused on the environmental perspective due to which the required attention of the government has not been achieved as the valuation of the possible loss occurring from the loss of ecosystem services has not been done yet.

From the earlier literature also, although various studies have used several approaches for the valuation based on the agricultural farmland, we are still unaware of any such study which will infer us about the cost the society and the nation will bear after the loss of ecosystem services which is a source of major flora and fauna and also the major source to one of the recreational sites of the country.

To understand the scope of Willingness to Pay in the forest of Panchase in Nepal, the following specific objectives will be fulfilled:

- To estimate the relationship between WTP and other socioeconomic variables.
- To derive a demand curve of the forest as a whole.

II. METHODOLOGY

A systemic research study needs to follow a proper methodology to achieve the predetermined objectives. The following method was carried out to fulfill the objectives of the study.

A. Theoretical Framework

According to Shogren et al., (2006) and McIntosh et al., (2007), a person's lifetime utility can be written as

$$\bar{U} = \int_0^{\tau} \bar{U}^0 e^{-\rho t} dt + \int_{\tau}^T \bar{U}^1 [c(t) - \alpha D [x(t) + \tilde{x}(t)], Q^1] e^{-\rho t} dt \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

U = Fixed level of utility

$\bar{U}^0$ = Constant Utility at good state

$\bar{U}^1$ = Utility in the bad state

ρ = Rate of time preference

c = Consumption in period t

D = Damage Function

τ = Invasion Time

T = Time of Death

α = Proportion of damage faced by the person

$\tilde{x}$ = All contributions to invasion control by other parties

x = Monetary contributions to invasion control

Q^1 = Environmental quality in bad state

Using envelope theorem in equation 3 to determine the WTP value, V:

$$V = -\frac{dW}{d\tau} = \frac{\partial L/\partial \tau}{\partial L/\partial W}$$

$$= \frac{-[U^1(c(\tau) - \alpha D(x(\tau) + \tilde{x}(\tau), Q^1) - \bar{U}^0)]e^{-\rho t} + \lambda [(-c(0) + c(\tau) + x(\tau))e^{-rt}]}{\lambda}$$

Allowing $c(0) = c(\tau)$, keeping c and x at their optimum level (provided by equations 4 and 5) and employing dual optimality condition in 6 to simplify allows value at $t = \tau$ to be determined as follows:

$$V = \frac{[\bar{U}^0 - \bar{U}^1 c(\tau) - \alpha D(x(\tau) + \tilde{x}(\tau)), Q^1]e^{-rt}}{[\bar{U}_{M^1}^1(c(\tau) - \alpha D(x(\tau) + \tilde{x}(\tau)), Q^1 * (1 - \alpha D_{\hat{x}})]/2} + x(\tau)e^{-rt} \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

We assume that $\bar{U}^0 > \bar{U}^1$ and $D_{\hat{x}} < 0$, V is always positive and equal to the difference in utility from a bad state to a good state.

B. Willingness to Pay Theory

Environmental goods and services provide benefits to humans in a similar manner as the market goods and services do. However, because of the public goods nature of environmental goods, many do not have markets and thus prices do not exist. By the nature of public goods, the major features discussed are rivalry and excludability. That is why; the exact value of the environmental goods and services is difficult to measure. Theoretical concepts of economic welfare used to evaluate the value of environmental goods include consumer surplus, compensating and equivalent variation, and compensating and equivalent surplus. Compensating surplus, which is a special case of compensating variation, is more appropriate for stated preference methods, as used in the present study because the response elicited in the present survey is one in which utility is assumed held constant given a change in income and the good being valued is a case of "restricted demand" (Kolstad, 2011).

C. Economic Specification of the Model

Generally, Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) studies include often an estimation of the WTP function or valuation function that function depends on income and other socio-economic characteristics of the respondents to the CVM. Therefore,

$$WTP = f(r) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

WTP = Willingness to Pay

r = Vector of explanatory variables (scenarios, income, and socio-economic characteristics)

D. Empirical Econometric Model

The Logit regression model has employed been employed for this study. The econometric model is as follows:

$$\ln P(WTP) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 Age + \alpha_2 Dep_{FamilyMembers} + \alpha_3 No_{ofVisits} + \alpha_4 Expenditure + \alpha_5 Assistance + \alpha_6 Cost_{LOSSRs} + \alpha_7 DiffX + \alpha_8 DiffY + Travel_{distance} \alpha_9 + e \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Where,

WTP = Willingness to Pay

α_0 = Intercept of the model

α_1 = Coefficient of age of respondent

α_2 = Coefficient of number of dependent family members

α_3 = Coefficient of number of times the members of households visit in the forest

α_4 = Coefficient of Expenditure

α_5 = Coefficient of Assistance

α_6 = Coefficient of Cost Loss

α_7 = Coefficient of difference of WTP from low impact to minimal of forest impact to households for one year

α_8 = Coefficient of difference of WTP from low impact for 10 years to low impact for one year

α_9 = Coefficient of distance from the nearest market

And,

Age = Age of the respondent

Dep_Family_Members = Number of dependent family members

No_of_Visits = Number of times the members of households visit the forest

Expenditure = Expenditure made by the household

Assistance = Money received by households, if any

Cost_Loss_in_Rs = Cost loss by the households

Diff X = Difference of WTP from low impact to minimal of forest impact to households for one year

Diff Y = Difference of WTP from low impact for 10 years to low impact for one year

Travel_distance = Distance from the nearest market

e = Error term

III. STUDY AREA

Panchase VDC, situated between (latitude: 28°10'55" to 28°15'56" North) and (longitude 83°48'03" to 83°49'53" East) is the study site. The Panchase Forest Area is very rich in plant diversity. There are five major forest types; Alder Forest, Chir Pine Broad Leaved Forest, East Himalayan Oak-Laurel Forest, Lower Temperate Oak Forest, and Schima-Castanopsis Forest. Kharsu (*Quereus semecarpifolia*), Phalat (*Quercus species*), and Lali Gurans (*Rhododendron arboretum*) are major species at the upper part of the area whereas Chilaune (*Schima walichii*), Katus (*Castanopsis indica*), Rakchan (*Daphniphyllum himalayense*), and Sal (*Shoerea robusta*) found at the lower belt. There are more than 589 flowering plant species recorded in the Panchase forest. 107 species of medicinal plants, 8 species of fiber yielding plants, 23 species of natural dye yielding plants; 18 wild species potential for floriculture (except Orchids), 56 species of wild mushroom, and 98 species of ferns are found in the area. This region is commonly known as the Kingdom of wild Orchids.

A. Research Design

Figure 1 is the flowchart portraying all the steps and procedures that has been carried out from the inception of the research to its completion.

Figure 1: Research Design

Source: Constructed by the authors

Open ended questionnaire was used for the survey. Questionnaire was divided into three sections: introduction, ecosystem services related questions and valuation questions. The introductory section asked respondents several demographic questions. The second section asked respondents about the ecosystem services they obtained from the forest and their recreational activities supported by the forest area.

The section also tried to take in their opinions regarding the management of forest conservation. Finally, the last section consisted of the questions regarding the willingness to pay scenarios of the local people. Primary as well as secondary data was collected applying the following tools and techniques. Primary data was collected using the questionnaire survey. For this purpose, an open-ended questionnaire was made for the valuation.

Three questionnaires were pre-tested in the area in 3 sample points. Then, the tested questionnaires were performed as face-to-face interviews to identify the WTP of the household and other information telling different impact scenarios. Literature review and required secondary data were collected from different books, journals, newspapers, research reports, and the internet.

This research had set some expected signs which played a major role in the research finding. The table below shows the independent variables used in the model, its description, and expected sign for the WTP to control the impacts of the unmanaged forest conservation. The dependent variable takes the value 1 if the people have the willingness to pay for the control of impacts otherwise it is zero (Table 1).

Table 1: Independent Variables with Expected Sign

SN	Variables	Description	Expected Sign
1	Age	Age of the respondent	+
2	Dependent Member	Number of dependent family members in the households	-
3	Number of Visits	Number of times household member visit the forest	+
4	Expenditure	Expenditure made by the household annually in Rs.	-
5	Assistance	Money received by households from NGOs, INGOs, help, if any	+
6	Economic Loss	Loss due to the damage created by the animals of the forest, have to travel long for recreation, etc.	+
7	Diff X	Difference of WTP from low impact to minimal of forest impact to households for one year	+/-
8	Diff Y	Difference of WTP from low impact for 10 years to low impact for one year	+/-
9	Travel Distance	Distance from the nearest market	-

Source: Created by authors

Collected data was processed with the help of Microsoft Excel 2010 and STATA 10 was used for the analysis and estimation purpose.

IV. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

A. Descriptive Statistics of Sample Characteristics

This section describes the variables used in the study and their obtained mean, median, minimum value, maximum value and standard deviation.

Table 2: Summary Statistics, Using the Observations 1-51

Variables	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
Age	45.86	46.00	94.00	24.00	12.13
Language	1.23	1.00	3.00	1.00	0.43
Gender	1.16	1.00	2.00	1.00	0.37
Schooling	11.86	12.00	15.00	0.00	2.23
Occupation	2.26	2.00	4.00	1.00	0.39
Income	2.18	2.00	4.00	1.00	1.12
Dep Family Member	1.42	1.00	5.00	0.00	1.26
Indep Family Member	2.69	2.00	6.00	1.00	1.01
Enjoy Nature	4.63	4.00	5.00	1.00	1.08
Env Science	1.89	2.00	3.00	1.00	0.58
Env System Change	1.23	1.00	2.00	1.00	0.23
Env Degradation	1.23	1.00	2.00	1.00	0.26
Benefit	1.09	1.00	2.00	1.00	0.24
Cost Loss	1.78	2.00	2.00	1.00	0.58
Cost Loss in Rs.	7856.23	2500.00	305000.00	0.00	36589.23
Fishing	2.36	2.00	3.00	1.00	1.59
Swimming	3.04	3.00	4.00	1.00	1.36
Recreation	2.97	3.00	3.00	1.00	1.56
Harm to Economy	3.88	4.00	6.00	1.00	1.52
Harm to Health	3.08	3.00	6.00	1.00	1.69
Harm to Forest	4.23	5.00	6.00	1.00	1.22
Harm to Watershed	4.55	5.00	6.00	1.00	0.95
WTP	0.96	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.23
Picnic	1.82	2.00	3.00	1.00	0.67
Praying	3.02	3.00	4.00	1.00	1.05
No of Visits	4.56	5.00	6.00	1.00	1.21
WTP1	1021.32	1000.00	5000.00	0.00	956.36
WTP2	856.36	500.00	5000.00	0.00	823.26
WTP3	1759.68	1000.00	12000.00	0.00	2658.96
Caste	1.58	1.00	3.00	1.00	0.74
Property	1.82	2.00	2.00	1.00	0.39
TV	1.17	1.00	3.00	1.00	0.38
Env Group	1.83	2.00	3.00	1.00	0.46
Tourists Duration Stay	2.65	2.00	4.00	1.00	1.24
Satisfaction Level	2.96	2.00	4.00	1.00	0.37
Expense Locality	7256.39	7500.00	10000	0.00	5623.65

Source: Field Survey

From Table 2, the overall summary of the data collection can be observed. Several variables are seen in the table which can elaborate on different issues. This study has focused on the prime aspect of the research study, i.e. to find the willingness to pay of the people regarding forest management. According to the table, for scenario one which

is to manage the forest to completely pacify all its impacts on households for one year, the mean WTP is NPR 1021.32 (Approx. US\$ 9.6). Likewise, the mean WTP for the second scenario which is to manage the forest targeting to keep its impact low for one year is NPR 856.36 (Approx. US\$ 8.1). Finally, the mean WTP for the final scene that is to keep the forest impact low for ten years in the sample point only is NPR 1759.68 (Approx. US\$ 16.6). Therefore, the conclusion derived from the above table is that people are ready to pay more for the first scenario in comparison to the second and third created scenarios.

B. Income Section Description

People of households in sample points have been involved in different major and minor income-generating activities for livelihood. To capture all of the respondents, four categories of the income group has been created (Table 3).

Table 3: Different Income levels with Frequency and Percent

Income/Year	Frequency	Percent
<1,20,000	11	21.57
1,20,000 to 2,40,000	14	27.45
2,40,000 to 3,60,000	20	39.22
>3,60,000	6	11.76

Source: Field Study

As presented in Table 3, the income of the household is divided into four categories where 21.57 percent of the respondents earn less than NPR 120,000 (US\$ 1132.08). 27.45 percent of the respondents earn between NPR 120,000 (US\$ 1132.08) and NPR 240,000 (US\$ 2264.15). 39.22 percent of the respondents earn between NPR 240,000 (US\$ 2264.15) and NPR 360,000 (US\$ 3396.23). Similarly, only 11.76 percent of the respondents earn more than NPR 360,000 (US\$ 3396.23).

Table 4: Income at Different level with its WTP Number of People

Income/Year	WTP _{No}	WTP _{Yes}
<1,20,000	1	9
1,20,000 to 2,40,000	0	10
2,40,000 to 3,60,000	6	15
>3,60,000	2	8

Source: Field Study

As presented in Table 4, among 51 respondents the low income and high income groups are less in number. That is why; the willingness to pay of the high and low income level groups is also not very likely. However, the medium income level groups are more in the sample and the likeliness to pay or the willingness to pay is also very high for the management of forests in different created scenarios.

C. Econometric Model with Empirical Values

As we know that WTP depends on socioeconomic factors, income and other variables. For this particular study, WTP acts as the binary dependent variable which takes value 1 if people are ready to pay and 0 otherwise. On the other side, socioeconomic factors, expenditure the proxy of income and other variables are used as independent variable. Logit regression model has been run, then analysis and interpretation is done accordingly.

Table 5: Results of Logit Regression Model

Dependent Variable WTP	Coefficient
Independent Variables	
Age	0.0272 (0.0365)
Dep_Family_Members	-0.0852 (0.265)
No_of_Visits	0.836** (0.0321)
Expenditure	-0.00125* (0.000369)
Assistance	-0.000235* (0.0000120)
Cost_Loss_Rs	0.000562 (0.000221)
Diff X	3.56e-06 (0.000563)
Diff Y	-0.000147 (0.000138)
Travel_Distance	0.000387 (0.000237)
Constant	0.524 (1.599)
Observations	51
Pseudo R ²	29.86 Percent

Source: Field Survey

Standard errors in parentheses; ***p<0.01, **p<0.05, *p<0.1

The results from the Logit analysis are presented in Table 5. The result indicates that among the various determinants of WTP only the number of the visit of the household member to the lake, expenditure, assistance, and cost of loss are significant at 10 percent and 5 percent where the number of visit and cost of loss is positively related to WTP and expenditure for household and assistance is negatively related to the WTP. For the variable age, as the age of the respondent increases by one year, the odds ratio in favor of WTP for the forest management is increased by NPR 0.0272 (US\$ 0.00026), and if dependent family member increases by one, the odds ratio in favor of WTP for the forest management decreases by NPR 0.0852 (US\$ 0.00080), keeping other variables constant. *Ceteris Paribus*, as the cost of loss, increases by one rupee the odds ratio in favor of WTP for the forest management increases by a negligible amount. The difference

of WTP from low impact to minimize the forest impact to least for one year in Nepali rupees is positively related to the WTP. Similarly, a difference of WTP from low impact for 10 years to low impact for one year in Nepali rupees is negatively related to the WTP. Also, the travel distance from the nearest market is positively related to WTP for the forest management increases by a negligible amount. And, besides that, the overall model is fit at 29.86 percent.

D. Demand Curve of the Forest

To derive the demand curve of the forest as a product, we need to find the trend of WTP and the elasticity of the curve which is also the slope of the demand curve.

Table 6: Different Elasticity of Econometrics Model

Dependent Variable WTP	Elasticities (E_y/E_x)
Independent Variables	
Age	.0325896
Dep Family Members	-.0056417
No of Visits	.2896547
Expenditure	-.0426741
Assistance	-.0002751
Cost Loss Rs	.0129573
Diff X	.0006521
Diff Y	.0239571
Travel Distance	0.568941

Source: Field Study

Table 6 portrays the elasticity section, the first elasticity of WTP (Ep_1) is 0.0652178 and the second elasticity of WTP (Ep_2) is 0.0239571 as estimated from the software. Both the elasticity points are less than unity. Therefore, it concludes that a relatively inelastic demand curve can be deduced. Furthermore, this demand curve is negatively sloped. The reason for being relatively inelastic demand curve might be that the intervention of the tourists is high in the area, the luring dominance showed by the NGO and INGO for the forest conservation in the region, and the concept that the government should take care of the forest and not them residing locally.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The Willingness to Pay (WTP) was positively related to the age of people, negatively related to the number of dependent family members, positively related to the number of visits that household members make to the forest area, negatively related to the expenditure of households in the forest area, negatively related to the assistance that the area receives from NGOs, INGOs, etc., positively related to the cost of loss occurred due to the unmanaged forest expansion and positively related to the distance from the nearest market.

The Panchase forest region is rich enough to incorporate all four types of ecosystem services known namely – Regulation Services, Provisioning services, Support services, and Cultural Services. The region is has been the source of food, fuel, and water for the

livelihood and surroundings which justifies its provisioning services. The climate of the region up to Pokhara city has been regulated by the forest area and water purification is also a major activity in the place which justifies its regulating services. The recreational and aesthetic values in the region due to the scenic viewpoint and the temple justifies its cultural services whereas the primary production of hundreds of species of flora and the luring soil formation mechanism justifies the supporting services.

The forest is in a normal good condition for the region because of the decreasing willingness to pay of the people for its conservation and thus, is a negatively sloped demand curve.

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